

Bioassay of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Nomuraea rileyi* (Deuteromycotina; Hyphomycetes) against the rice leaffolder (LF)

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Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia* spp. are infected with various entomogenous fungi, including *Beauveria bassiana*, *Nomuraea rileyi*, *Paecilomyces farinosus*, and an unidentified entomophthorean species. These fungi are obligate insect pathogens that might be useful in biological control of LF.

We tested the virulence of *B. bassiana* (white muscardine fungus) and *Nomuraea rileyi* (cosmopolitan pathogen of lepidoptera) on LF *C. medinalis*. The *B. bassiana* isolate originated from the brown planthopper from China, the *N. rileyi* isolate originated from hairy caterpillar *Rivula atimeta* in the Philippines.

Suspensions of 0, 10⁴, 10⁵, 10⁶, 10⁷, and 10⁸ conidia/ml were prepared for both fungi. Thirty 3d-instar LF larvae were dipped in each suspension and left for several minutes on filter paper. Treated larvae were incubated in petri

Mortality of LF larvae treated with different entomogenous fungi. IRRI, 1987.

dishes containing rice leaves; the leaves were renewed daily. Mortality was determined after 1 wk incubation.

Mortality percentage was adjusted, using Abbott's formula. Differences between fungi species were tested by probit analysis. Probit analysis resulted

in ED₅₀ of 7.4 × 10³ conidia/ml for *B. bassiana* and ED₅₀ of 3.5 × 10⁵ conidia/ml for *N. rileyi*.

Virulence of these fungi differed (see figure). The *B. bassiana* isolate was more infectious to this host. □

Effect of buprofezin in controlling green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV) incidence

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We evaluated an insect growth regulator, buprofezin, in the field against *Nephotettix virescens* GLH population and RTV infection.

Two formulations were used: wettable powder (WP) and emulsifiable concentrate (EC), each at 250, 500, and 1,000 g (ml)/ha. The trial was conducted at Maros in the dry season and at Lanrang in the 1986 wet season in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 5 ×

Table 1. GLH population and RTV incidence at Maros, Indonesia, 1986.

Buprofezin concentration g (ml)/ha	Formulation	GLH ^a (no./40 hills)		Tungro incidence (%)	
		28 DT	49 DT	56 DT	63 DT
250	10 WP	12.7 a	7.0 a	51	83
500	10 WP	13.2 a	12.7 ab	60	78
1000	10 WP	11.5 a	5.7 a	54	81
250	400 EC	14.0 ab	11.0 ab	49	79
500	400 EC	21.7 b	14.5 ab	53	83
1000	400 EC	14.2 ab	8.0 a	45	68
0 (control)	—	36.7 c	20.0 b	66	87

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P 0.05.

10 m. Variety Cisadane was planted at 25-× 25-cm spacing. Urea and TSP were applied at 40 kg N and 18 kg P/ha 25 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). The insecticide was applied first when GLH was found on trial plots. Counts were made from 1 d after insecticide

application to 49 DT in Maros and 53 DT in Lanrang. RTV incidence was monitored weekly until symptoms were found.

At Maros, GLH was found 21 DT at 8-17 insects/40 hills. At 28 DT, all insecticide rates significantly controlled